

1 Supporting information

2 **Internal Flames: Metal(Ioid) Exposure Linked to Alteration of Lipid Profile in Czech**
3 **Male Firefighters (CELSPAC-FIREexpo Study)**

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13 Contamination, Climate, and Human Health

14 **Sample collection and storage**

15 Recruitment occurred at the Training Center of the Fire Rescue Service in Brno (Czechia) for
16 PROF and NEW FF, and at the Faculty of Sport, Masaryk University, Brno for CTRL.

17 Blood samples were collected by medical personnel in an operational ambulance. Urine samples
18 were collected at the workplace by own urine collection following the instruction of medical personnel.
19 In phases 1 and 3, morning void midstream urine was sampled, along with venous blood on an empty
20 stomach. In phase 2, the sampling of morning void urine and venous blood on an empty stomach was
21 not possible due to training schedule.

22 Venous blood for serum isolation was sampled in 7.5 mL S-Monovette® tube containing the Z-
23 gel clotting activator. Each participant provided approximately 40 mL of midstream urine, which was
24 collected in a 50 mL centrifuge tube. Both the venous blood and urine samples were immediately
25 transported to laboratories in a cooling box set at 8°C.

26 Once the clot had formed in the venous blood tube, it was centrifuged at 2500×g and 20°C for 10
27 minutes. Subsequently, 0.5 mL aliquots were separated and placed into 1.2 mL cryotubes, which were
28 then gradually frozen and stored in a biobank facility at -80°C for further analyses of the biomarkers
29 and biochemical analysis. Similarly, the urine samples in 50 mL centrifuge tubes were divided into 1
30 mL aliquots in 1.2 mL cryotubes, frozen gradually, and stored in a biobank facility at -80°C until further
31 analyses.

32 **Table S1** – Results from the questionnaires ¹.

		NEW FF	PROF	CTRL
Participants that filled out questionnaires		59	52	55
Age (years)	Median	24.5	28	26
	10th - 90th perc.	21 - 31	23 - 33	20 - 32
	Min. - Max.	19 - 34	20 - 35	18 - 35
BMI (kg/m²)	Median	26.3	26.2	24.6
	10th - 90th perc.	22.6 - 30.3	22.9 - 29	21.6 - 28.6
	Min. - Max.	20.7 - 33.4	21.1 - 32.2	18.4 - 30.9
Health (subjective assessment, %)	Always healthy and well	50.9	67.3	56.4
	Mostly healthy and well	49.2	32.7	41.8
	Often do not feel well	0	0	1.8
Job (%)	Firefighter	100	100	0
	Student	0	0	45.5
	IT	0	0	14.6
	Office	0	0	12.7
	Other	0	0	27.2
Length of firefighting career (years)	Median	0.5	3.3	0
	10th - 90th perc.	0.25 - 1	1 - 10	0
	Min. - Max.	0 - 5	0.5 - 14	0
Smoking (%)	Yes	0	0	0
	No	100	100	100
Former smoking (%)	Yes	11.9	19.2	7.3
	No	88.1	80.8	92.7
If a former smoker (years since quitting)	Median	4	0.5	3.5
	10th - 90th perc.	0.5 - 10	0.2 - 5	0.6 - 8
	Min. - Max.	0.5 - 10	0.1 - 6	0.6 - 8
Contact with a large fire in the last 6 months (%)	Two or more times	22	59.6	5.5
	One time	32.2	21.2	0
	Never	45.8	19.2	90.9
Contact with firefighting foams in the last year (%)	Two or more times	0	34.6	0
	One time	25.4	40.4	1.8
	Never	69.5	25	98.2
Diet (%)	Mixed diet	100	100	100
	Vegetarian	0	0	0
	Vegan	0	0	0
Use of food supplements (%)	Yes	27.1	17.3	56.4
	No	72.9	82.7	43.6

34 **Quality control and quality assurance**

35 The concentration of three metals (Cd, Hg, and Pb) and one metalloid (As) in urine samples was
36 determined by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Agilent 8900 ICP-MS/MS, Agilent
37 Technologies) after 10x dilution of samples by solution containing deionized water, a nonionic
38 surfactant Triton X-100 (0.04%), ammonia (1%), butanol (2%), EDTA (0.04%), and the appropriate
39 internal standards for ICP-MS/MS (20 ng/mL of Sc, Ge, In, Lu and Bi).²

40 The samples underwent analysis at the Trace Analytical Laboratory at RECETOX MU (Brno, Czech
41 Republic). This laboratory is accredited under ISO 17025.

42 Method was validated by analysis of samples spiked with known amount of analyte and by analysis of
43 following certified reference materials (SERO AS, Norway): Seronorm™ Trace Elements Urine Level
44 1 and Seronorm™ Trace Elements Urine Level 2. Laboratory blanks (diluted aliquot of DI water) and
45 certified reference materials (CRMs) were consistently analysed through the analytical sequence with
46 frequency approximately one blank and one reference material for every 10 - 15 samples. The ICP-
47 MS/MS measurements demonstrated recoveries typically ranging from 91 % to 112 % for both the
48 spiked samples and the certified reference materials. Relative standard deviations calculated by
49 repeatedly analysed CRMs during the measurement of the entire data set were within the range of single
50 units of percent. Limits of detection for As, Cd, Hg and Pb were as follows: 0.03, 0.01, 0.01 and 0.02
51 ng/mL. Laboratory and method performances were successfully verified by participation in third-party
52 proficiency testing, namely ICI-EQUAS under HBM4EU project and INSTAND EQUAS organized by
53 German Medical Association.

54 The levels of total cholesterol (CHOL, mmol/L), low-density lipoprotein (LDL, mmol/L), high-density
55 lipoprotein (HDL, mmol/L), and triglycerides (TG, mmol/L) were measured spectrophotometrically with
56 an Alinity c instrument (©Abbott, Illinois, U.S.A) in the private accredited laboratory, which conform
57 the Quality Management system standard EN ISO 9001:2015.

58 **Table S2** – Formulas used for correction of urine metal(loid)s for urine dilution³.

Adjustment of metal(loid) levels for creatinine was performed by following formula:

$$c_{metal(loid)_{creat}} = \frac{c_{metal(loid)}}{c_{creat}}$$

where $c_{metal(loid)_{creat}}$ is creatinine adjusted metal(loid) urine concentration [$\mu\text{g}_{metal(loid)} / \text{g}_{creatinine}$],
 $c_{metal(loid)}$ is metal(loid) concentration in urine [ng/ml], and c_{creat} is urine creatinine concentration
[g/l].

SG-corrected concentrations were calculated using following formula:

$$C_{SG} = \frac{C_i \times (SG_{ref} - 1)}{SG_{meas} - 1}$$

where C_{SG} is the concentration standardized on SG, C_i is the measured concentration, SG_{meas} is the measured specific gravity, and SG_{ref} is the reference SG value. As a reference SG value, a mean SG value for all cohorts was used (1.02).

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60 **Figure S1** – Directed acyclic graph ⁴

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62 **Table S3** – Urinary levels of metal(loid)s (ng/mL) adjusted for specific gravity in complete population
 63 (“All”) and stratified for sub-cohorts (“CTRL” – control sub-cohort, “PROF” – sub-cohort of
 64 professional firefighters, “NEW FF” – sub-cohort of new firefighters in training)

All (n=164)	DF	Mean	Sd	Min	Pctile[25]	Median	Pctile[75]	Max
As_sg	100%	13	16	2.5	4.9	6.3	13	102
Cd_sg	100%	0.13	0.068	0.036	0.085	0.11	0.15	0.4

Hg_sg	100%	0.55	0.68	0.034	0.12	0.29	0.68	3.3
Pb_sg	100%	0.85	0.49	0.061	0.53	0.74	1.1	3.2
CTRL								
(n=54)								
As_sg	100%	15	19	2.6	5.5	7.8	14	102
Cd_sg	100%	0.13	0.071	0.036	0.083	0.11	0.17	0.38
Hg_sg	100%	0.44	0.47	0.034	0.13	0.25	0.54	2.5
Pb_sg	100%	0.69	0.52	0.21	0.38	0.54	0.78	3.2
PROF								
(n=52)								
As_sg	100%	14	18	2.7	5	6.1	11	70
Cd_sg	100%	0.14	0.075	0.044	0.089	0.12	0.18	0.4
Hg_sg	100%	0.66	0.86	0.039	0.12	0.31	0.74	3.3
Pb_sg	100%	0.86	0.39	0.061	0.59	0.83	1.1	2.2
NEW FF								
(n=58)								
As_sg	100%	11	11	2.5	4.2	6	12	52
Cd_sg	100%	0.12	0.057	0.036	0.085	0.1	0.14	0.33
Hg_sg	100%	0.55	0.66	0.038	0.12	0.29	0.72	2.9
Pb_sg	100%	1	0.5	0.26	0.66	0.88	1.2	2.7

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66 **Table S4** - Urinary levels of metal(loid)s ($\mu\text{g/g}$ of creatinine) adjusted for creatinine in complete
67 population (“All”) and stratified for sub-cohorts (“CTRL” – control sub-cohort, “PROF” – sub-cohort
68 of professional firefighters, “NEW FF” – sub-cohort of new firefighters in training)

All (n=164)	DF	Mean	Sd	Min	Pctile[25]	Median	Pctile[75]	Max
As_crea	100%	8.04	10.2	1.17	2.7	4.27	7.27	65.4
Cd_crea	100%	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.09	0.22
Hg_crea	100%	0.32	0.41	0.01	0.08	0.19	0.39	2.11
Pb_crea	100%	0.5	0.26	0.06	0.31	0.44	0.64	1.42
CTRL								
(n=54)								
As_crea	100%	8.18	11.1	1.37	2.67	4.57	7.54	65.4
Cd_crea	100%	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.16
Hg_crea	100%	0.23	0.21	0.01	0.08	0.14	0.35	1
Pb_crea	100%	0.35	0.21	0.09	0.25	0.3	0.38	1.26

PROF

(n=52)

As_crea	100%	9.58	12	1.76	3.17	4.44	8.46	46.6
Cd_crea	100%	0.09	0.04	0.03	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.22
Hg_crea	100%	0.42	0.52	0.03	0.08	0.23	0.46	2
Pb_crea	100%	0.57	0.26	0.06	0.4	0.52	0.71	1.42

NEW

(n=58)

As_crea	100%	6.53	6.85	1.17	2.47	3.59	6.51	33.7
Cd_crea	100%	0.07	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.19
Hg_crea	100%	0.33	0.41	0.02	0.07	0.18	0.39	2.11
Pb_crea	100%	0.58	0.26	0.17	0.39	0.54	0.7	1.38

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70 **Figure S2** – Spearman correlation matrix.

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72 **Table S5** – Associations between population characteristics and SG-adjusted urinary metal(loid)s.

73 Expressed as relative change in urinary metal(loid)s per unit change in population characteristics. **Bold**

74 refers to statistical significance (p<0.05)

Characteristics	As		Cd		Hg		Pb	
	β	p-value	β	p-value	β	p-value	β	p-value
Age	-5.47	0.487	27.08	0.001	22.47	<0.001	31.71	<0.001
BMI	17.04	0.003	-4.71	0.308	1.36	0.698	-10.43	0.031
Sub-cohort								
CTRL	reference		reference		reference		reference	
PROF	-6.42	0.571	9.89	0.397	2.85	0.760	31.43	0.010
NEW FF	-15.85	0.131	-10.45	0.309	5.45	0.514	54.93	<0.001
Length of FF career	-3.45	0.350	5.05	0.142	-0.18	0.940	9.02	0.017
Contact with fire in the last 6 months								
Never	reference		reference		reference		reference	
One time	-15.20	0.188	-6.29	0.588	2.85	0.760	30.24	0.023
Two or more times	-8.68	0.410	-0.23	0.982	5.45	0.514	13.57	0.214
Former smoking								
no	reference		reference		reference		reference	
yes	16.47	0.280	30.02	0.050	-0.60	0.953	13.79	0.328

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77 **Table S6** – Associations between urinary metal(loid)s ([ng/mL], categorized into quartiles) and serum
78 lipids from regression models: β -coefficients and p-values. The model was adjusted for age, BMI,
79 former smoking, length of firefighting career and sub-cohort (CTRL/PROF/NEW FF). Q1 – Q4:
80 quartile 1 – quartile 4. **Bolt** refers to statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Results are expressed as percent
81 change in lipid biomarker associated with quartile (Q2-Q4) compared to reference (Q1).

		CHOL		LDL		HDL		TG	
		β	p-value	β	p-value	β	p-value	β	p-value
As	Q1	<i>reference</i>							
	Q2	9.34	0.401	3.67	0.747	8.32	0.541	-2.26	0.853
	Q3	2.67	0.803	4.95	0.663	-6.34	0.609	-8.31	0.480
	Q4	23.32	0.046	21.85	0.073	-5.00	0.689	9.52	0.455
Cd	Q1	<i>reference</i>							
	Q2	-9.27	0.351	-9.49	0.361	-16.99	0.132	6.19	0.620
	Q3	8.18	0.458	8.12	0.482	-13.34	0.259	8.82	0.493
	Q4	3.01	0.782	7.37	0.527	-29.90	0.006	0.71	0.955
Hg	Q1	<i>reference</i>							
	Q2	-2.93	0.779	-8.41	0.427	4.15	0.75	-10.37	0.366

	Q3	5.56	0.616	10.03	0.394	-14.68	0.217	-4.42	0.713
	Q4	7.15	0.529	7.16	0.545	-19.22	0.111	15.28	0.258
Pb	Q1	<i>reference</i>							
	Q2	11.69	0.295	20.34	0.096	-0.82	0.949	14.72	0.261
	Q3	30.97	0.013	33.15	0.012	17.92	0.212	31.19	0.030
	Q4	25.46	0.041	23.85	0.066	11.07	0.444	33.49	0.025

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83 **Table S7** –Associations between urinary metal(loid)s (ng/mL) and serum lipids from MLR and
84 BWQS models performed on reduced dataset (n=106, only CTRL and PROF): β -coefficients and 95%
85 confidence intervals (CI, for MLR) and credibility intervals (CrI, for BWQS). The model was
86 adjusted for age, BMI, former smoking, length of firefighting career and sub-cohort (CTRL/PROF).
87 **Bolt** refers to statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

	CHOL	LDL	HDL	TG
	β (95% CI/CrI)	β (95% CI/CrI)	β (95% CI/CrI)	β (95% CI/CrI)
As	5.35 (-5.9 , 17.94)	5.14 (-6.14 , 17.77)	-7.31 (-18.69 , 5.66)	-0.9 (-12.45 , 12.17)
Cd	8.28 (-3.83 , 21.92)	8.9 (-3.32 , 22.67)	-10.72 (-21.97 , 2.17)	5.85 (-7.09 , 20.59)
Hg	3.16 (-12.23 , 21.25)	3.62 (-11.91 , 21.88)	-20.18 (-33.48 , -4.22)	20.56 (1.42 , 43.31)
Pb	13.69 (0.83 , 28.2)	10.42 (-2.23 , 24.71)	14.24 (-0.46 , 31.12)	24.16 (9.33 , 40.99)
BWQS	14.7 (2.98 , 28.07)	20.34 (2.12 , 40.98)	-10.85 (-25.07 , 10.44)	15.28 (2.75 , 29.81)

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89 **Table S8** –BWQS mixture composition estimates: weights (percentage rescaled between 0 to 1) for
90 each component of metal(loid) mixture (M-M) and metal(loid)-OH-PAH mixture (M-PAH-M) in
91 CHOL, LDL, HDL and TG. Intensity of the colour indicates increasing weight.

	CHOL		LDL		HDL		TG	
	M-M	M-PAH-M	M-M	M-PAH-M	M-M	M-PAH-M	M-M	M-PAH-M
As	0.307	0.116	0.258	0.136	0.163	0.106	0.173	0.095
Cd	0.187	0.091	0.207	0.110	0.421	0.127	0.152	0.094
Hg	0.188	0.101	0.214	0.109	0.321	0.117	0.248	0.127
Pb	0.319	0.145	0.322	0.111	0.096	0.099	0.427	0.155
1-OH-Naph	-	0.104	-	0.130	-	0.092	-	0.088
2-OH-Naph	-	0.121	-	0.133	-	0.094	-	0.101

1-OH-Pyr	-	0.090	-	0.063	-	0.096	-	0.083
2,3-OH-Phen	-	0.071	-	0.060	-	0.087	-	0.088
2-OH-Fluo	-	0.086	-	0.081	-	0.088	-	0.093
3-OH-Fluo	-	0.076	-	0.067	-	0.093	-	0.077

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93 **Table S9** – BWQS results for metals-OH-PAH mixture. **Bold** refers statistical significance (<0.05).

Mixture (Metal(loid)s + PAHs)				
	β	95% CrI		
CHOL	16.36	3.50	31.12	*
LDL	18.81	4.56	35.73	*
HDL	-2.31	-18.81	14.08	
TG	10.97	-2.47	27.81	

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